

Effects of combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine as adjuncts to peripheral nerve blocks: a systematic review with meta-analysis and Trial Sequential Analysis - SUPPLEMENT

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Summary of findings:

Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine compared to placebo for increasing duration of analgesia?

Patient or population: increasing the duration of analgesia?
Setting: Patients undergoing surgery with a peripheral nerve block
Intervention: combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine
Comparison: placebo

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	N _e of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with placebo	Risk with combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine				
Duration of analgesia	The mean duration of analgesia was 665 minutes	MD 460 minutes higher (249 higher to 671 higher)	-	120 (2 RCTs)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^a	Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine probably increases duration of analgesia when compared with placebo.
Duration of the motor block	The mean duration of the motor block was 848 minutes	MD 66 minutes higher (88 higher to 274 higher)	-	115 (2 RCTs)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^a	Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine probably increases duration of the motor block when compared with placebo.
Duration of the sensory block - not reported	-	-	-	-	-	
Cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption assessed with: Intravenous morphine equivalents	The mean cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption was 8.4 milligram	MD 13 milligram lower (23.5 lower to 2.4 lower)	-	334 (4 RCTs)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine versus placebo may reduce cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption but the evidence is very uncertain.
Serious adverse events	not pooled	not pooled	not pooled	80 (1 RCT)	⊕○○○ Very low ^c	
Adverse events	253 per 1,000	172 per 1,000 (46 to 648)	RR 0.68 (0.18 to 2.56)	164 (3 RCTs)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,d}	Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine may reduce the risk of adverse events but the evidence is very uncertain.

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the relative effect of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; MD: mean difference; RR: risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.

Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.

Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: the true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Explanations

a. Most trial results were at high risk of bias. Therefore, we downgraded by '1' point due to risk of bias.

b. Trial Sequential Analysis showed that we had insufficient information to confirm/reject a 33% relative change, less than 50% of the required information size was reached. Therefore, we downgraded by '2' points due to imprecision.

c. Serious adverse events were only reported in 1 trial with a 5% control group event rate, resulting in extreme imprecision.

d. Trial Sequential Analysis showed that we insufficient information to confirm/reject a 25% relative risk change, less than 50% of the required information size was reached. Therefore, we downgraded by '2' points due to imprecision.

Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine compared to dexmedetomidine for increasing duration of analgesia?

Patient or population: increasing duration of analgesia?

Setting:

Intervention: combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine

Comparison: dexmedetomidine

Outcomes	N _o of participants (studies) Follow-up	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
				Risk with dexmedetomidine	Risk difference with combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine
Duration of analgesia	268 (4 RCTs)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^a	-	The mean duration of analgesia was 741 minutes	MD 388 minutes higher (211 higher to 565 higher)
Duration of the motor block	50 (1 RCT)	⊕⊕○○ Low ^a	-	The mean duration of the motor block was 587 minutes	MD 7 minutes lower (146 lower to 133 higher)
Duration of the sensory block	50 (1 RCT)	⊕⊕○○ Low ^a	-	The mean duration of the sensory block was 555 minutes	MD 73 minutes higher (54 lower to 200 higher)
Cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption assessed with: Intravenous morphine equivalents	58 (1 RCT)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	-	The mean cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption was 23.2 milligram	MD 10.9 milligram lower (18.9 lower to 2.9 lower)
Serious adverse events - not reported	-	-	-	-	-
Adverse events	230 (3 RCTs)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b,d}	RR 0.98 (0.64 to 1.51)	183 per 1,000	4 fewer per 1,000 (66 fewer to 93 more)

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; MD: mean difference; RR: risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.

Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.

Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: the true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Explanations

- a. Only one trial at high risk of bias reported on this outcome. Therefore, we downgraded by '2' points due to risk of bias.
- b. Trial Sequential Analysis showed that less than 50% of the required information size was reached without breaching any monitoring boundaries. Therefore, we downgraded by '2' points due to imprecision.
- c. Serious adverse events were only reported in 1 trial with a 5% control group event rate, resulting in extreme imprecision.
- d. Trial Sequential Analysis showed that we insufficient information to confirm/reject a 25% relative risk change, less than 50% of the required information size was reached. Therefore, we downgraded by '2' points due to imprecision.

Duration of analgesia

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Aliste 2022						
Albrecht 2023						
Chassery 2020						
Hong 2019						
Hong 2021						
Kang 2019						
Maagaard 2023						
Rodrigues 2021						
Zhang 2019						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

Forest plot of the meta-analysis of the duration of analgesia subgrouped according to comparator. DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Best/worst-case scenario of duration of analgesia.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Worst/best-case scenario of duration of analgesia.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

**Forest plot of the meta-analysis of the duration of analgesia including the study by Kang et al.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.**

Subgroup analysis for trials using dexamethasone as control according to type of surgery.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of duration of analgesia for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Mode of administration = intravenous

Hong B	2019	1266	390	20	654	192	20	612	[421; 803]	40.3%
Hong B	2021	904	467	29	560	222	29	344	[156; 532]	40.5%
Rodrigues D	2021	1669	1236	65	1182	1153	65	487	[76; 898]	19.2%
Total (random-effects, 95% CI)				114			114	479	[301; 657]	100.0%

Heterogeneity: Tau = 101; Chi² = 3.85, df = 2 (P = 0.15); I² = 48%

Test for overall effect: Z = 5.27 (P < 0.01)

Mode of administration = perineural

Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	602	108	20	222	[155; 288]	100.0%
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Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 7.05, df = 1 (P < 0.01)

Subgroup analysis for trials using dexmedetomidine as control according to administration.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

**Mean Difference
IV, Random, 95% CI**

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Risk of bias = High

Hong B	2019	1266	390	20	654	192	20	612	[421; 803]	26.0%
Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	602	108	20	222	[155; 288]	35.4%
Hong B	2021	904	467	29	560	222	29	344	[156; 532]	26.2%
Rodrigues D	2021	1669	1236	65	1182	1153	65	487	[76; 898]	12.4%
Total (random-effects, 95% CI)				134			134	388	[211; 565]	100.0%

Heterogeneity: Tau = 148; Chi² = 16.05, df = 3 (P < 0.01); I² = 81%

Test for overall effect: Z = 4.30 (P < 0.01)

Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 0.00, df = 0 (P = NA)

Subgroup analysis for trials using dexmedetomidine as control according to risk of bias.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Type of surgery = Upper extremity

Hong B	2019	1266	390	20	654	192	20	612	[421; 803]	40.3%
Hong B	2021	904	467	29	560	222	29	344	[156; 532]	40.5%
Rodrigues D	2021	1669	1236	65	1182	1153	65	487	[76; 898]	19.2%
Total (random-effects, 95% CI)				114			114	479	[301; 657]	100.0%

Heterogeneity: Tau = 101; Chi² = 3.85, df = 2 (P = 0.15); I² = 48%
 Test for overall effect: Z = 5.27 (P < 0.01)

Type of surgery = Truncal

Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	602	108	20	222	[155; 288]	100.0%
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Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 7.05, df = 1 (P < 0.01)

Subgroup analysis for trials using dexmedetomidine as control according to type of surgery.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of duration of analgesia for the comparison with dexmedetomidine.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Type of local anesthetic = long

Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	440	110	20	384	[318; 451]	67.8%
Maagaard M	2023	1574	811	39	953	365	41	621	[343; 899]	32.2%
Total (random-effects, 95% CI)				59			61	460	[249; 671]	100.0%

Heterogeneity: Tau = 126; Chi² = 2.64, df = 1 (P = 0.10); I² = 62%

Test for overall effect: Z = 4.27 (P < 0.01)

Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 0.00, df = 0 (P = NA)

Subgroup analysis for trials using placebo as control according to local anesthetic.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Mode of administration = perineural

Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	440	110	20	384	[318; 451]	100.0%
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Mode of administration = intravenous

Maagaard M	2023	1574	811	39	953	365	41	621	[343; 899]	100.0%
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Test for subgroup differences: $\text{Chi}^2 = 2.64$, $\text{df} = 1$ ($P = 0.10$)

Subgroup analysis for trials using placebo as control according to administration.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Mean Difference
IV, Random, 95% CI

Risk of bias = High

Zhang P 2019 824 105 20 440 110 20 384 [318; 451] 100.0%

Risk of bias = Low

Maagaard M 2023 1574 811 39 953 365 41 621 [343; 899] 100.0%

Test for subgroup differences: $\text{Chi}^2 = 2.64$, $\text{df} = 1$ ($P = 0.10$)

Subgroup analysis for trials using placebo as control according to risk of bias.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Study or Subgroup	Year	DXDM		Control			MD	95% CI	Weight
		Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD			

Type of surgery = Truncal

Zhang P	2019	824	105	20	440	110	20	384	[318; 451]	100.0%
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Type of surgery = Lower extremity

Maagaard M	2023	1574	811	39	953	365	41	621	[343; 899]	100.0%
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Test for subgroup differences: $\text{Chi}^2 = 2.64$, $\text{df} = 1$ ($P = 0.10$)

Subgroup analysis for trials using placebo as control according to type of surgery.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Duration of the motor block

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Aliste 2022						
Albrecht 2023						
Hong 2021						
Kang 2019						
Maagaard 2023						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

Forest plot of the meta-analysis of the duration of motor block subgrouped according to comparator. DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

-600 -200 0 200 400 600

Favours control Favours DXDM

Worst/best-case scenario of duration of motor block.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of duration of motor block for the comparison with placebo.

Doi plot for the assessment of duration of motor block for the comparison with dexamethasone

Duration of the sensory block

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Study						
Aliste 2022						
Albrecht 2023						
Hong 2021						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

 High

 Some concerns

 Low

Doi plot for the assessment of duration of sensory block for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Albrecht 2023						
Chassery 2020						
Hong 2021						
Kang 2019						
Maagaard 2023						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

**Meta-analysis of the cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption subgrouped according to comparator.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.**

Best/worst-case scenario of cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Worst/best-case scenario of cumulative 24 hour opioid consumption.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Trial Sequential Analysis for combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine for cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption. The analysis showed insufficient information to confirm/ reject a 5mg relative change. No boundaries were reached, nor the required information size.

Doi plot for the assessment of cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption for the comparison with placebo.

Doi plot for the assessment of cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Adverse events

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Aliste 2022						
Chassery 2020						
Hong 2021						
Kang 2019						
Maagaard 2023						
Rodrigues 2021						
Zhang 2019						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

Meta-analysis of adverse events subgrouped by type of comparator.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Best-worst case sensitivity analysis of adverse events.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Worst–best case sensitivity analysis of adverse events.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Incidence in control group 23.1%, RRR 25%, alpha 5%, beta 20%, diversity 41.2% is a Two-sided graph

Incidence in control group 27.8%, RRR 25%, alpha 5%, beta 20%, diversity 20.0% is a Two-sided graph

Doi plot for the assessment of adverse events for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Doi plot for the assessment of adverse events for the comparison with dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of adverse events for the comparison with placebo.

Pain at 24 hours

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Albrecht 2023						
Chassery 2020						
Hong 2021						
Kang 2019						
Maagaard 2023						
Zhang 2019						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

Meta-analysis of pain at 24 hours subgrouped according to comparator.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Best/worst-case scenario of pain at 24 hours.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Worst/best-case scenario of pain at 24 hours.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of pain at 24 hours for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Doi plot for the assessment of pain at 24 hours for the comparison with dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of pain at 24 hours for the comparison with placebo.

Pain at 48 hours

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Albrecht 2023						
Chassery 2020						
Maagaard 2023						
Zhang 2019						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

 High

 Some concerns

 Low

Study

Best/worst-case scenario of pain at 48 hours.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Worst/best-case scenario of pain at 48 hours.

DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Doi plot for the assessment of pain at 48 hours for the comparison with placebo.

Doi plot for the assessment of pain at 48 hours for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Pain at 72 hours

Risk of bias domains

Study

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Maagaard 2023						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

 Low

Cumulative 48-hour opioid consumption

Risk of bias domains

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Albrecht 2023						
Chassery 2020						
Maagaard 2023						
Zhang 2019						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

High

Some concerns

Low

Study

**Meta-analysis of the cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption subgrouped according to comparator.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.**

Best/worst-case scenario of cumulative 48 hour opioid consumption.
DXDM = Combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine.

Trial Sequential Analysis for combined dexamethasone and dexmedetomidine versus placebo for cumulative 48-hour opioid consumption. The analysis showed insufficient information to confirm/reject a 10mg relative change. No boundaries, nor the required information size, was reached.

Doi plot for the assessment of cumulative 48-hour opioid consumption for the comparison with dexamethasone.

Doi plot for the assessment of cumulative 48-hour opioid consumption for the comparison with placebo.

Cumulative 72-hour opioid consumption

Risk of bias domains

Study

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Maagaard 2023						

Domains:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

 Low

